

Predictive Analysis of Acute Respiratory Infections in San Juan de Lurigancho (2000-2024): A Comparative Study Using KNN, Random Forest, and XGBoost

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Abstract—Acute Respiratory Infections (ARIs) are a known public health challenge in San Juan de Lurigancho, the most populous district in Peru. This investigation presents a comparative and predictive analysis of ARI cases of timeline data, using three Machine Learning algorithms: K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Random Forest, and Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost). After careful hyperparameter tuning, XGBoost were the superior model achieving a Coefficient of Determination (R^2) of 0.710 and a Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of 209.35 cases. It improved the results of both the Random Forest model (MAE of 212.37 cases) and the KNN baseline (K=1, MAE of 219.16 cases). These models were trained and evaluated using historical epidemiological and environmental data to predict infection trends and These results demonstrate that gradient boosting techniques can effectively capture the complex, non-linear patterns of respiratory diseases in heavy populated urban areas. These results provide a clearer predictive framework for local health authorities to optimize resource allocation and proactive medical responses.

Index Terms—*Acute Respiratory Infections, K-Nearest Neighbors, Machine Learning, Random Forest, Time Series Forecasting, XGBoost*

I. INTRODUCTION

Acute Respiratory Infections (ARIs) are one of the main causes of morbidity globally and a critical public health challenge in Peru [1]. The evolution of these diseases are constantly monitored through the National Epidemiology Network (RENACE) and the National Center for Epidemiology, Prevention and Disease

Control (CDC PERU). Specifically, the district of San Juan de Lurigancho, being the most populous in the country, presents demographic and environmental dynamics that facilitate the quick spread of respiratory pathogens. In this spectrum, the incidence of ARI cases without pneumonia (*ira_no_neumonia*) constitutes a high volume of medical consultations, frequently saturating primary care health facilities during seasonal peaks.

Historically, epidemiological surveillance of ARIs has relied on the retrospective analysis of weekly bulletins. Even so, this reactive approach severely limits the anticipatory response capacity of health authorities. In last years, Machine Learning has emerged as a powerful tool for time series forecasting in epidemiology, overcoming the limitations of traditional statistical models by successfully capturing non-linear relationships and complex patterns. Despite their growing improvement, there is no universal consensus on which algorithm is the most efficient for processing real-world tabular epidemiological data, which often contain noise, outliers, and underreporting.

However, the main objective of this paper is to conduct a rigorous comparative analysis of the predictive performance of three Machine Learning algorithms: K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Random Forest [2], and Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) [3]. Using the

online historical data from CDC PERU of the district of San Juan de Lurigancho between 2000 and 2024, this study evaluates the capacity of each model to accurately predict the incidence rate of non-pneumonia ARI cases. By contrasting the error metrics and the overall robustness of these three techniques, this research provides an empirically grounded computational framework to optimize early warning systems and public health decision-making.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Collection

The dataset utilized in this study was downloaded by the National Center for Epidemiology, Prevention and Disease Control (CDC PERU) through the National Epidemiology Network (RENACE). The original dataset contains a full volume of nationwide health records, containing 2,240,129 rows and 14 columns, with historical data ranging from the year 2000 to 2024 [1]. These records include detailed epidemiological variables such as geographical location, epidemiological weeks, and specific stratifications of respiratory diseases.

B. Data Preprocessing

To isolate the specific dynamics of the target area, the used dataset was exclusively filtered for the district of San Juan de Lurigancho. A strict chronological ordering was applied, sorting the records first by year and then by epidemiological week. A subset of relevant features was formally defined and extracted into a new dataframe to optimize computational efficiency. Finally, the data was grouped by year and week, and the target variable—the total number of non-pneumonia ARI cases (*ira_no_neumonia*)—was aggregated using a summation function to construct a coherent and continuous time series for our predictive models.

C. Experimental Setup

To a better evaluating the predictive performance of the Machine Learning models

(XGBoost, Random Forest, and KNN), the preprocessed dataset was separated into a training set (80%) and a testing set (20%). A controlled random sampling approach was implemented using a fixed random state (`random_state=42`) to guarantee the reproducibility of the experimental results. After that, the predictor variables were standardized using *StandardScaler* from the Scikit-learn library [4]. This applied a z-score transformation, centering the data to a mean of zero and scaling it to a standard deviation of one ($z = (x - \mu)/\sigma$). Crucially, to prevent any potential data scope the standard scaler was fitted exclusively on the training set before transforming both the training and testing sets.

III. RESULTS

A. Predictive Performance Comparison and Temporal Analysis

To evaluate the effectiveness of these proposed models, the three selected algorithms were tested on the unseen 20% of the dataset. The performance was measured using the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and the Coefficient of Determination (R^2). This progression of the models predictive capabilities is summarized in Table I, and their temporal behavior against the actual data cases is seen in Fig. 1.

TABLE I. PREDICTIVE PERFORMANCE OF EVALUATED MODELS

algorithm	type of method	MAE	R^2
K-Nearest Neighbors	Based on distance (Baseline)	219.16	0.594
Random Forest	Bagging	212.37	0.649
XGBoost	Boosting	209.35	0.710

The baseline model, K-Nearest Neighbors (K=1), got the highest error with a MAE of 219.16. Theoretically this was predictable by relying exclusively on local distance similarity (the single nearest neighbor), KNN is highly susceptible to noise and random fluctuations inherent in epidemiological data. As seen in the temporal analysis (Fig. 1), its predictions are

erratic and fail to capture the underlying trend better.

The Random Forest ensemble model significantly improved the predictive accuracy, reducing the MAE to 212.37 and raising the R^2 to 0.649. By utilizing the bagging (Bootstrap Aggregating) technique this model constructs multiple independent decision trees and averages their outputs, efficiently reducing variance. However, as is characteristic of averaging methods, Random Forest tends to underestimate positive outliers. Fig. 1 clearly shows how the Random Forest line struggles to reach the real size of extreme seasonal peaks.

Lately, Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) proved to be better, achieving the lowest MAE of 209.35 and the highest R^2 of 0.710. Unlike the static averaging of Random Forest, the boosting technique builds trees sequentially where each new tree learns and corrects the residual errors (bias) of the previous one. This adaptive capability allowed XGBoost to closely fit the complex, non-linear nature of the time series, accurately following the real peaks of respiratory infections (Fig. 1).

To validate the statistical robustness of the predictions, a Residual Analysis was conducted by plotting the actual cases against the predicted values for the three models (Fig. 2). The diagonal red line represents the theoretical perfect prediction.

The KNN panel displays a high dispersion of data points, showing its high error rate. In contrast, the optimized XGBoost panel reveals a much denser and more symmetrical concentration around the perfect prediction line, showing significantly higher explained variance.

However, Fig. 2 also exposes a fundamental limitation shared by all three computational algorithms. The presence of an atypical value of 7,000 actual cases, no model was able to reach a prediction near to the red line, therefore underestimating the severity of this massive outbreak. It suggests that anomalous peaks of such magnitude may be driven by external variables (e.g., sudden epidemics or extreme climatic anomalies) that are not captured solely by chronological training features.

FIG. 1. COMPARISON OF THE PREDICTIVE MODELS (KNN, RANDOM FOREST, AND XGBOOST) AGAINST THE ACTUAL TIMELINE OF NON-PNEUMONIA ARI CASES IN SAN JUAN DE LURIGANCHO.

B. Residual Analysis and Outlier Behavior

Residual Analysis: How close are we to Perfect Prediction?

FIG. 2. RESIDUAL ANALYSIS OF THE EVALUATED ALGORITHMS SHOWING ACTUAL VS. PREDICTED CASES. THE RED DIAGONAL LINE REPRESENTS PERFECT PREDICTION ACCURACY.

C. Hyperparameter Optimization

The optimal performance of XGBoost was strictly proved through a cross-validation technique (Grid Search CV=3). The final desing of the model was consolidated with a *learning_rate* of 0.05 and a *max_depth* of 7, achieving an algorithmic balance that prevented overfitting while proved to be able to capture the complexity of the disease patterns in San Juan de Lurigancho. The number of boosting rounds (*n_estimators*) was changed at 100, and the subsample ratio was configured to 0.8 to improve generalization.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrated a comparative efficacy of Machine Learning algorithms in predicting Acute Respiratory Infections (ARIs) in high populated urban environments like San Juan de Lurigancho. The empirical evaluation revealed that traditional distance-based algorithms, like the KNN, are insufficient for capturing the volatile dynamics of epidemiological time series. While ensemble bagging approaches such as Random Forest helped reduce predictive variance, Extreme Gradient Boosting proved to be the most efficient model in this study. By

iteratively correcting residual errors, the optimized XGBoost configuration achieved the highest predictive accuracy showing a strong ability to capture seasonal patterns in infection cases.

However, the residual analysis revealed an important limitation very common in time-series forecasting: the tendency to underestimate extreme outbreak events. None of the evaluated models were able to accurately reproduce the weird large peak of nearly 7,000 reported cases. This suggests that such high epidemiological events are likely influenced by external factors beyond the temporal patterns captured in the dataset.

Future work should improve model performance by incorporating additional variables, particularly environmental and climatic indicators. Factors such as humidity, temperature variability, and air pollution levels (e.g., PM2.5) that could help explain sudden fluctuations in respiratory infection cases and improve the model's sensitivity to unexpected outbreaks.

From a public health perspective, the use of the optimized XGBoost model could support a shift

from reactive monitoring to more proactive planning. With reliable short-term forecasts, local health authorities and primary care centers could anticipate increases in acute respiratory infection (ARI) cases and prepare accordingly, allocating medical staff, hospital beds, and essential medications in advance of expected peaks.

V. REFERENCES

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